
ETHNOBOTANICAL INSIGHTS INTO MEDICINAL TREES AND THEIR CULTURAL SIGNIFICANCE IN KEBBI STATE

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>This study evaluated the medicinal value and traditional uses of tree species in Kebbi State, Nigeria. Data were gathered through structured questionnaires and direct field observations from 360 respondents across multiple villages. Forty-five medicinal tree species representing 21 families were documented, with the Anacardiaceae family being the most prevalent. Leaves and bark were the most commonly used plant parts, often combined with other ingredients to treat a variety of ailments. The majority of respondents were male, aged 41–50 years, married, predominantly farmers, and had limited formal education. Knowledge of medicinal tree cultivation was largely self-taught; only a small proportion of respondents reported planting trees specifically for medicinal purposes—20.83% in Kebbi South, 22.5% in Kebbi North, and 25% in Kebbi Central. Most trees were planted primarily for environmental protection rather than medicinal use. Preparation methods mainly involved decoctions administered one to three times daily, depending on the ailment. These findings reveal a rich diversity of medicinal trees and extensive traditional knowledge, emphasizing the urgent need for conservation strategies to sustainably manage and preserve this ethnobotanical heritage.</p>	<p>Medicinal trees, ethnobotany, traditional knowledge, conservation, Kebbi State</p>

INTRODUCTION

Ethnobotany is the study of how communities of a particular region employ indigenous plants for food, clothing, medicine and other activities. The documentation of this is crucial for the conservation and utilization of biological resources. Plant materials have been a major source of natural therapeutic remedies and are used to treat various infectious diseases in many developing countries (Kayode and Omotoyinbo, 2009). Thus, African flora is greatly rich with a lot of medicinal plants which indigenous people are familiar with and used over time. In African countries, the majority of the population uses traditional medicine for the treatment of various diseases and ailments like malaria, typhoid, ulcers, skin diseases, diabetes, reproductive problems, aches, and pains and various socio-cultural and economic reasons (Aiyeloja and Bello, 2006). Medicinal plants are naturally grown

plants which are commonly used in the prevention and curing of different illnesses affecting the health status of human beings. These plants grow as wild plant species in a spontaneous self-maintaining population in natural or semi-natural ecosystems. Sometimes it may be domesticated plant species through human actions such as selection or breeding with proper management for their existence (Anselem,2004) Medicinal plants play a key role in the development and advancement of modern studies by serving as a starting point for the development of novelties in drugs (Cowan, 1999). Nigerian is rich in biodiversity which is a veritable source of pharmaceuticals and therapeutic properties, though some of the plants are not adequately documented. However, in recent times, the pressures from deforestation, land degradation, unsustainable arable land use, urbanization and industrialization are taking their toll on the natural resources (Obute and Osuyi, 2002; Kayode, 2006).

Therefore the need for proper documentation of traditional medicinal practices among the people in Nigeria where published information has been scarce is immediately called for and this accounts for the rationale for undertaking the present study. Kebbi State is an area that is very rich in flora due to its location in the northern Guinea vegetation belt of the country. The use of plants for various purposes is widespread in this location. It is therefore the responsibility of the scientific community to unravel and document this information for the use of man. This study represents an attempt to document information on the traditional medicinal plants used in Kebbi state. A compiled checklist of these plants including their location, Latin names, families, parts used, uses, and names in the study area is the main purpose of this study. The documentation of medicinal uses of African plants is becoming increasingly urgent because of the rapid loss of the natural habitat for some of these plants due to anthropogenic activities.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Study area

The study was conducted in Kebbi State. It is situated in the extreme northwestern part of Nigeria; the area lies between latitude 12°44'59''N and longitude 4°32'45''E. It covers approximately 18,591K², supporting a population of about 2,757,544 million people. The mean annual temperature is between 35°C to 40°C, annual rainfall range from 450-1050mm and relative humidity ranges from 51-79% and 10-25% during rainy and dry season respectively. The vegetation is Sudan savannah type, and the soil is the semi-arid type, characterized by frequent weathering and leaching due to poor soil structure and low organic matter content.

Sampling Technique and Sample Size

The study was conducted in the three senatorial districts in Kebbi State. Multistage sampling was used to select ten respondents from three villages from two districts each from two local governments of each of the senatorial districts in Kebbi state. Respondents will comprise local herb sellers, farmers, forest officers and hunters who provided information on different tree species, parts used and different modes of preparation for the treatment of different ailments in the study area.

Method of data collection

A structured questionnaire was used to collect data from the selected respondents based on the objectives of the study. In each of the villages' interviews were conducted to determine group consensus on the medicinal plant species. Key informants made up of herb sellers and forestry officers were interviewed to identify plants and provide additional information on the use of medicinal plants in the study area.

Data Analysis

Data collected from the respondents was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as Tables, Frequency, and Percentages.

RESULT

A total of 45 medicinal tree species from 21 families are identified and used for treating different ailments in the study area. Most of these species were wild and harvested for their leaves and bark. The remedies were administered mainly through oral pain and baths. The family Anacardiaceae was represented by (6) species followed by Moraceae (5), Caesalpiniaceae (4), Fabaceae, Mimosaceae, Myrtaceae, and Combretaceae (3) and other families.

Table 1: Medicinal Trees Identified in the Study Area

S/N	Botanical name	Common name	Family	Uses	Part used and preparation
1	<i>Khaya senegalensis</i>	African mahogany	Fabaceae	De	DysenteryBark soaked in water
2	<i>Sclerocarya birrea</i>	Manila	Anacardiaceae	Sore throat	Decoction of leaves is taken orally
3	<i>Balanite aegyptiaca</i>	Desert date	Balanitaceae	Dysentery and stomach pr	and problemsDecoction of bark
4	<i>Azadirachta</i>	Neem tree	Meliaceae	Stomach ache, fever	dysenteryDecoction <i>indica</i> and de of leaves
5	<i>Vitex doniana</i>	Black	Verbenaceae	Increase milk flow	Fruits are eaten raw plum
6	<i>Moringa Moringa</i>	Moringaceae	Hypertension and	Boiled leaves and <i>oleifera</i>	blood tonic seeds
7	<i>Ficus glucose</i>	African mustard	Moraceae	Malaria	Boiled leaves
8	<i>Ficus polita</i>	Ficus	Moraceae	Stomach ache and	Boiled leaves, bark chest pain and roots
9	<i>CCassiasiebe</i>	African	Caesalpinia	Dysentery and	Boiled roots <i>riana</i> laburnum eae stomach ache
10	<i>Khaya</i>	Winter	Meliaceae	Chronic dysentery	Bark soaked in water <i>ivorensis</i> thorn and weakness of the body
11	<i>Acacia nilotica</i>	Acacia	Mimosaceae	Dysentery and ulcer	Boiled leaves
12	<i>Ficus platyphylla</i>	GGutta-peachtree	Moraceae	Malaria	Boiled bark
13	<i>Citrus aurantifolia</i>	Lime	Rutaceae	Typhoid	Boiled leaves
14	<i>Daniella oliveri</i>	African copaiba	Caesalpinia	Dysentery	Boiled bark
15	<i>Calatropis</i>	SSodomap	Asclepiadace	Treat gonorrhoea	Roots soaked in water <i>procera</i> ple ae
16	<i>Adansonia</i>	Baobab	Bombacacea	Treat diarrhoea and	Dried leaves are <i>digitata</i> e chest pain pounded into pap and Fresh leaeatenare made raw
17	<i>Mangifera</i>	Mango	Anarcardiace	Treat malaria	Decoction of leaves <i>indica</i> ae typhoid and fever
18	<i>Psidium</i>	Guava	Myrtaceae	Treat malaria	Decoction of bark and <i>guajava</i> leaves
19	<i>Vitellaria paradox</i>	Shea butter	Sapotaceae	Treat malaria	Boiled bark

- 20 *Ficus ovate* Ficus Moraceae Treat malaria Boiled leaves
- 21 *Prosopis* Iron tree Mimosaceae smallpoxllpoxx Boiled bark and *africana* leaves
- 22 *Diospyros* Jackal Ebenaceae General body pain Decoction of left *mespiliformis* berry with fatigue orally at
- 23 *Gueira* Moshi Combretacea Treat sore throat Boiled leaves *senegalensis* plant e and boost milk flow
- 24 *Pakia* Locus Mimosaceae High blood pressure Soaked bark
biglobosa bean tree
- 25 *Detarium* Tallow Fabaceae Stomach pain Decoction of leaves
microcarpum tree
- 26 *Ceiba* Fuma Malvaceae Stomach problems Boiled stem *pentandra* and diarrhoea
- 27 *Combretum* Bush Combretacea Treatment of Boiled leaves and root *molle* willows e asthma and chest pain
- 28 *Jatropha* Termite Euphobiacea Treatment of Boiled root and leaves *curcas* plant e typhoid, malaria, fever
- 29 *Neocarya* Plum tree Chrysobalan Treatment of Decoction of bark and *macrophylla*
aceae toothache leaves
- 30 *Bombax* Red silk Bombacacea Malaria Boiled bark
Buonopolens cotton tree
- 31 *Piliostigma* Camels Fabaceae Stomach pain Decoction and *thonningii* foot infusion of leaves and bark
- 32 *Anogeissuss* African Combretacea Body pain Infusion and *leiocarpus* birth e associated with decoction of leaves fatigue for bathing and drinking
- 33 *Ficus* Ficus Moraceae Cold and sore throat Boiled bark
iteophylla
- 34 *Nauclea* African Rubiaceae Gonorrhoea and Boiled roots
latifolia peach stomach pain
- 35 *Tamarindus* Tamarine Caesalpinia Treatment of Skin Decoction of leaves *indica* eae
cancer Stomach and roots taken orally problems and and for bathing
- 36 *BBauhiniaruf* Orchid bush Caesalpinia Fever and dysentery Boiled roots with *escens* eae potash totally rally
- 37 *Sterculia* Gum tree Malvaceae Hypertension, Decoction of leaves *setigera* blood tonic and and bark is taken body Weakness orally
- 38 *Citrus* Sweet Rutaceae Treatment of fever, Decoction of stem and *sinensis* orange Headache and leaves toothache
- 39 *Holarrhena* Connessi Apocynaceae Treatment of Decoction of bark and *floribunda* dysentery, roots is taken orally diarrhoea and skin and a bath infection
- 40 *Lannea acida* Plum Anacardiaceae Treatment of pile In Decoction of fresh mango eae
children leaves is taken orally
- 41 *Gmelina* Gmelina Verbenaceae Treatment of fever Decoction of leaves, *arborea* Malaria and typhoid bark and stem

42	<i>Terminalia</i>	Large Combretacea	Cough and sore	Warm decoction of	ollis	leaves e	throat leaves
43	<i>Eucalyptus</i> <i>Citriodora</i>	Lemon scented scented	Myrtaceae	Treatment of cold, malaria and typhoid	Warm decoction of	leaves	
44	<i>Melaleuca leu- dendron</i>	Cajeput tree	Myrtaceae	Cough	Decoction of leaves		
45	<i>Anacardium</i> <i>occidentale</i>	Cashew	Anacardiaceae	Fever and body weakness	decoction of fresh	leaves	

DISCUSSION

Most of the tree species identified in the study area were found to have multiple uses. The respondents use to extract different parts of the trees for medicinal purposes to treat various ailments. The leaves constituted the bulk of the parts used which is in line with the assertion of Kayode *et al*, (2009) that the leaves formed the major parts of the ethnobotanicals used in the traditional treatment of diseases. This was also in line with the report of Bello (2016) that leaves, seeds, barks and roots of plants were used to solve men's sexual problems. The findings of Kayode (2008) in his study on a survey of plant barks used in native pharmaceutical extraction also corroborate this result. The most common family is Anacardiaceae which is used for treating different ailments such as *Sclerocarya birrea* (manila) for the treatment of Sore throat, *Mangifera indica* for the treatment of malaria, typhoid and fever, *Lannea acida* for treatment of pile in children, *Ficus glumosa* for treatment of Malaria. This is mainly through the decoction of their leaves for drinking in the morning and/or evening.

The leaves, barks and roots of *Anacardium occidentale* were found to be active in the treatment of fever and body weakness through decoction. *Mangifera indica* leaves and bark are also active as a cure for fever. The leaves, bark and stem of *Gmelina arborea* are found to be effective in the treatment of fever Malaria and typhoid. *Moringa oleifera* is good for curing wounds, boils, swellings, and low blood pressure, as a blood tonic, lowers blood sugar levels in diabetic patients.

Psidium guajava leaves mixed with *Mangifera indica* leaves and/or bark together with lemon grass and *Anacardium occidentale* leaves or bark is effective for the treatment of malaria according to the group interview conducted and key informants in the study area. Juice extracted from the leaves of *Azadirachta indica* is good for treating measles and pimples. The above discussions corroborate the findings of (Olanipekun and Kayode 2010), (Bello 2016) and (Fayemi and Kayode 2010) in their studies on using medicinal plants to treat different diseases.

Conclusion

Medicinal plants were highly utilized in the study area. The parts mostly used are the leaves, barks, fruits and roots through decoction and drinking once, twice or thrice daily depending on the nature, types or intensity of the ailments. The most commonly used family is Anacardiaceae. It was found that most of the trees have multiple uses and are prepared with different combinations of herbs for effectiveness. The result of the study also shows that there is a high diversity of medicinal trees and traditional knowledge on the use, preparation and application, which is still maintained among local people in the study area. More trees, herbs and shrubs are used for medicinal purposes in the study area. And this shows that there is a need for urgent conservation of these medicinal trees for sustainability.

Recommendation

Due to the continuous loss of diversity of medicinal tree species in the study area owing to pressure on them by the people as a result of deforestation, charcoal, fire, and farming, various methods of species conservation such as natural regeneration and afforestation should be given a priority through incentives and provision of nursery materials to the people. Various organizations such as governments and NGOs must ensure an integrated approach to tree multiplication and propagation through policies programs and enlightenment campaigns on the medicinal values of tree species in the study area.

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